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The First Appearances in the History of Uzbek Children's Reading: "Avesta," "Haftiyak."

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***Abstract:** The article "Early Appearances in the History of Uzbek Children's Reading" covers the development of children's literature in Uzbekistan. In particular, it analyzes the early stages of children's reading, the social and cultural factors that influenced its formation. The article examines the beginnings of Uzbek children's literature in ancient times, including the development of folk oral literature and early written sources. The article also discusses the early examples of children's literature, their content and educational significance. The formation of Uzbek children's literature during the analyzed period and other elements of national and world culture that influenced it play an important role. The article serves as the main source for identifying the historical initial steps in the development of children's reading.*

***Key words:** Avesta, Haftiyak, children's literature, early books, historical context.*

Introduction

In the history of Uzbek children's reading, the first manifestations are based mainly on oral folk literature, traditional fairy tales, epics, parables, and legends. The formation of children's reading among the Uzbek people has a very long history. The beginning of this process began to develop gradually, often at the beginning of the 20th century, especially at the beginning of the Soviet period.

1. Oral folk literature:

The first forms of Uzbek children's literature originated from oral creativity. During this period, fairy tales, parables, and legends were passed down orally to children. Folk oral literature is enriched with stories and fairy tales, which have educational value, especially for children. These works played an important role in the development of children's consciousness and the formation of moral values.

2. Folk tales and epics:

Uzbek folk tales and epics contain various moral lessons for children. These tales often depicted the struggle between heroes, angels, evil, and good character. Uzbek folk tales contain educational and moral ideas for children, teaching them proper behavior, friendship, patriotism, and appreciation of labor.

3. Scientific and pedagogical works:

At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, Uzbek children's literature first appeared in written form. Scientific and pedagogical works for children have begun to be created in the Uzbek language. During this period, educational and instructional books were published for children. Books tried to inform children about moral values, the importance of education and learning.

4. The first books for children:

At the beginning of the 20th century, especially under the influence of the Soviet government, the process of publishing books in Uzbek children's literature began to develop. The first books of Uzbek children's reading, taking into account pedagogical approaches, sought to provide children with information about science, history, and moral values.

Results and Discussion

The first manifestations of Uzbek children's reading were mainly based on folk oral literature and the first forms of written literature, and works containing moral and educational ideas for children were created. The continuation and development of this process subsequently led to major achievements of Uzbek children's literature in the 20th century.

The Avesta is one of the oldest written sources in the world and provides valuable information about the history, way of life, customs, religions, and spirituality of the peoples of Central Asia in ancient times. It was founded by Zoroaster, the last edition of which was completed in the 6th century AD. Thus, the Avesta encompasses events spanning over several millennia, containing not only religious information but also historical events. Therefore, the Avesta is the main source for studying the ancient culture (beliefs, language, literature), and partially the history of the peoples of Central Asia and Iran. In Zoroastrianism, Ahura Mazda occupies a special place as an eternal and everlasting deity. In general, it is said that all goodness is created by Him. The evil opposite of every good creature is created in the image of Ahriman. In general, as Professor I. Khojamurodov writes, in the "Avesta," good and evil, light and darkness, good and evil are described as opposing forces in the images of Ahura Mazda and Ahriman. In the "Avesta", religious and mythical ideas are combined with early philosophical views. On this basis, the idea of forming a spiritually and morally perfect person, a combative, just person capable of maintaining harmony and goodness, occupies a central place. Indeed, the Avesta contains many immortal ideas, teachings, and instructive thoughts aimed at shaping the spiritual world of man. The sacred source also mentions the names of many places in Central Asia. Some notes and references, names and terms in this monument, as well as individual chapters of "Bindahshin", indicate that even when the first sprouts of Zoroastrianism began to appear, spirituality, education, and upbringing were quite developed in the regions where the peoples of modern Maverannahr and Khorasan lived. "Education", states the Avesta, "must be considered the most important (support) pillar of life. It is necessary to educate every young person in such a way that they rise to the highest level first by learning to read well and then to write". According to Professor H.Homidiy, during that period, our ancestors strictly adhered to the customs of "lagomzadan" (to water a horse), "zin zadan" (to saddle a horse), and "kamarbastan" among all tribes and clans. For example,

in tribes engaged in animal husbandry, crafts and skills related to this field were taught more: girls were required to know how to spin yarn from wool, work with spindles and spinning wheels, weave various clothes, sew, and obtain wool, while boys were required to know thirty-two military skills, such as grazing, breeding and giving birth to livestock, caring for camels and horses, driving flocks to distant pastures, protecting livestock from wild animals and pirates. After acquiring these skills, girls passed the "lagomza" and "zin zadan" exams at the age of 15, and boys at 17. As a result, they reached adulthood, learned to manage the household, and gained the right to become "kadbonu" (housewife), "kad xudo" (head of the household, head of the family), receive the shepherd's coat, ride horses, and ride camels. The most gifted young men were specially trained in horsemanship and participated in military exercises. As the Avesta scholar G. Makhmudova writes, "The moral ideas recorded in the Avesta are a mixture of the earliest moral concepts that existed in the primitive communal system, which changed, enriched, and developed in subsequent periods in accordance with socio-historical conditions".

The spirit of goodness, described in the "Avesta," is the power of creation, creation, and the spirit of evil leads to destruction and destruction. Goodness is a symbol of life, filling the earth with useful animals and plants, enlightening human life with health, strength, happiness and joy, hope and faith, beauty and good thought, abundance. Evil is the opposite, the opposite. The sacred source glorifies goodness, creativity, and virtue, emphasizing that for a person to do good, they must love and cherish the land, as well as be active and truthful. Only then, thanks to human activity and knowledge of one's work, the world of goodness will increase, and a person will be freed from the layer of evil, darkness, and oppression in their heart. In the Gohlar section of the Avesta, the god of goodness, Ahura Mazda, says: "Only those who lead others to goodness will be blessed with goodness..." Grant us, under the rays of truth, the enlightenment created by Good Intention, so that we may rejoice in every moment, every hour, every day of our existence. Great attention in the "Avesta" is paid to the fact that thoughts about goodness, enlightenment, and virtue take root in people's hearts and ensure their purity. "When", says the instruction, "Good Intention came to me and I heard Your words for the first time, I acknowledged that it is extremely difficult to carry them among people." But I will carry to the end Your most virtuous word. After that, I considered You pure. All parts of the "Avesta" are imbued with feelings of respect for humanity: to love and cherish all the blessings of life on earth and in heaven is considered a sacred duty and obligation for a person. In the "Avesta", the legacy of our ancestors, special attention is paid to the upbringing of children. In their opinion, a well-mannered child is capable of anything. That is, a well-mannered child is, first of all, disciplined. They believed that discipline was the foundation of all good deeds. For this reason, they paid serious attention to improving their children's work skills and teaching them crafts. The value and significance of these tasks in the sacred book have increased even more today, because the results of the creative work being carried out in our country largely depend on the talent, potential, initiative, dedication, patriotism, and enlightenment of our youth. If children's upbringing is not established from an early age, it is difficult to change it even after they grow up. Therefore, a child should be cared for carefully from a young age. As the First President of our Republic, Islam Karimov, noted in his work "High Spirituality - Invincible Force," long-term scientific observations and research show that a person receives 70 percent of all information received during their lifetime by the age of 5. Considering that a child's consciousness is mainly formed at the age of 5-7, it is during this period that the first sprouts of spirituality begin to appear in their heart under the influence of the family environment. The wise proverb of our people "A bird does what it sees in its nest" clearly confirms this eternal truth. "Indeed, as our people say", A child starts from the beginning," the upbringing in childhood is different and impactful. It was during this period that our ancestors deeply understood that children begin to

understand and comprehend good and evil, and that concepts of Good and Evil are formed in their tender hearts, and they tried to grow the seeds of goodness in their children's hearts. These immortal ideas are vividly and convincingly depicted in our cultural monument "Avesta.

"Children," says the historical source, "must be taught from an early age to plant trees, make household tools, cultivate the land, and engage in animal husbandry." ("Avesta". Yasna, 19, 43, 68-Hots, pages-18, 22, 57, 63, 76, 86, 96) In the sacred source, the performance of the above-mentioned tasks was made mandatory, transformed into mandatory means. Our ancestors have always glorified labor, because labor is the foundation of all wealth, the cause of all abundance, the creator of all delicacies. Labor is, first of all, a very important educational tool. "Goodness", says the divine book, "must work, create material delicacies with its own hands. "On the contrary, those who did not work were criticized, they were included among the lowest people. At the same time, it is emphasized that blessings flee from lazy people. "A person who does not work", says the "Avesta," "you will truly bow your head to foreign doors like beggars for eternity. "Indeed, they carry various crops past you, and all these bounties are destined for a household that works and lives prosperously. It will be so forever and ever! "Man", says the Avesta, "will receive the favor of God or his helper only if he contributes to the multiplication of livestock, the flourishing of pastures, and works diligently in agriculture and irrigation". In particular, in the Mithra ode of the Avesta, there are many odes dedicated to the flourishing of pastures and the multiplication of livestock. As written in the sacred source: Blessings, praise, joy, and honor to Mithra, the master of boundless pastures, and to Ramana, the master of good pastures. Ahura Mazda spoke: Sipiytmom said to Zarathustra: "I created Mithra thus - Its pasture is boundless, I am Ahura Mazda worthy Of worship and praise He too is entirely worthy. We worship Mithra, whose pastures are boundless. These thoughts from the sacred source provide valuable information about how our ancestors placed special importance on raising their children to be well-mannered and moral, and teaching them professions from an early age. These exemplary works were carried out for the happiness and well-being of their children, for their future. That is why they especially emphasized that young people should be well-mannered, knowledgeable and intelligent, hardworking, faithful, enlightened, and well-mannered. After the official adoption of the religion of Zoroastrianism, that is, the belief in the one God, attention to education in our country increased even more. Special schools under royal jurisdiction were opened in temples - fire temples, madrasa-type educational institutions were organized, and their educational system was developed; such subjects as mathematics, astronomy, medical science, history, jurisprudence, and hygiene were increasingly introduced into the educational process; special attention was paid to the education and upbringing of youth, and their spiritual development. According to researchers (H. Homidiy, G. Makhmudova), in the education and upbringing of youth, it is envisaged that every Zoroastrian should be raised with purity, honest behavior, honest hands, and optimism. Based on these needs and requirements, the "Avesta" defines the duties of educators, teachers, and teachers, repeatedly emphasizing that the most important burden of society is entrusted to them. As a result, teachers and teachers were divided into "good" and "bad" teachers depending on how well they have mastered their knowledge, attitude to their profession, eloquence, resourcefulness, dedication, laziness, indifference and irresponsibility. As noted in the "Avesta," good teachers raise "healthy-minded children, brave, wise sons and daughters who know different languages, sons who can protect the nation from calamities, a generation that can see a good future, a bright life with clear eyes." It awakens love for their religion, people, and homeland in young people's hearts, teaches them to earn their living through honest work, and morality, cooperation, and wishing only good for people are transmitted to students only from wise teachers. As stated in the sacred source, a good teacher should guide young people to the right path, guide them on the path of goodness, and instill love for life in their hearts. In the Avesta, the need to

pay special attention to the upbringing of girls is emphasized in several places: "Girls should seriously engage in the study of knowledge and wisdom compared to boys. Because while they are in their parents' household, they should organize and beautify their father's household, and when they reach their spouse's destination, they should be engaged in raising children, education, and nurturing future generations. "In the sacred source, special attention is paid to the fact that every child should engage in any profession, be occupied, and work. Also, begging while in need of others was condemned.

Based on this requirement, our ancestors paid serious attention to the connection of education with practice. The Avesta states that "with the improvement of food, the morality and manners of the people also strengthen. "Because positive changes in morals and manners also affect their upbringing. Special emphasis is placed on the fact that the basis of all good deeds and creativity in the world is labor. In most passages of the Hot and Yasht parts of the Avesta, goodness is contrasted with evil, justice with oppression, and wisdom with ignorance, the first is praised, and the second is condemned as a vice, just as good teachers are contrasted with ignorant teachers. A bad teacher, due to their indifference, lack of wisdom, and lack of effort in improving their knowledge and skills, leads to the intellectual growth and impoverishment of the younger generation's spirituality: "With their incorrect teaching, they discourage people from the best deeds." The Avesta condemns bad educators, criticizing them for leading young people astray from the right path: "A bad educator, with their teaching, distorts divine words and ruins the perception of life. "Indeed, it deprives people of the priceless capital of truth and the Good Intention. In reality, they are the ones who push life into baseness. They elevate the deceitful dervishes to the skies, considering them great. They deprive women and men of the benefit of divine words. O Mazda! They become obstacles for the righteous ones on the path of truth. With these teachings, they prohibit people from their most righteous deeds. They scatter the life of the people of the worlds with their misleading judgments. In historical sources, a bad teacher turns people away from the right path, leads them towards ignorance, cannot see the prosperity of the Homeland, the creative work of people, looks askance at those who cultivate the land, plow it, sow crops with honest labor, engage in horticulture, farming, multiply livestock, and create, depriving people of invaluable traditions. According to researchers, in the "Avesta", special attention is paid to the fact that a person is obliged throughout his life to preserve water, soil, air, fire, in general, all good things in the world, pure and whole. Moreover, the Avesta glorifies humanity and the struggle for human happiness. In particular, the following ideas were put forward: The purity of intentions and thoughts is promoted in the spirit of good thought, divine law, kindness to one's neighbor, readiness to help in need and danger, readiness to actively fight against evil, for the happiness of people, striving to live in friendship and community with fellow believers in harmony with everyone. Special attention is paid to the fact that a person should not envy others in his thoughts, and attention is paid to the fact that people with good intentions always glorify goodness in their practical activities, promote enlightenment, and on this basis play an important role in the fight against ignorance in society". Justice, truth, goodness, creativity, enlightenment, and the upbringing of children have always been in the focus of our ancestors. The criterion of truth is righteousness and honesty. That is why truth is praised and glorified in the Avesta. Because our ancestors knew well that where truth prevails, mutual trust and kindness prevail, and there are conditions for stability, peace, and development, and therefore they paid special attention to instilling these ideas in the minds of their children and raising them to be well-mannered and moral. These life-giving wisdoms of the "Avesta" continue to serve people selflessly and enrich them spiritually today. The reforms being carried out in the spiritual and educational sphere in our country during the years of independence, the exemplary work being carried out to study the rich history, cultural and spiritual heritage of our people, and their use in the upbringing of youth is a requirement of today. The immortal ideas of spirituality and education, put forward in the great

spiritual heritage of our ancestors - the "Avesta," are still important in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation.

HAFTIYAK (Persian - one-seventh) - a book containing one-seventh of the Holy Quran. For the convenience of young reciters, several (13-14) surahs of the Quran were selected and compiled into a recitation book. It is considered the first manual that served as an anthology in schools in Turkestan in the past. Children were taught it after mastering the Arabic alphabet. Usually, the Haftiyak was taught for 1-2 years. After the Haftiyak, they began reading the Holy Quran. It became customary to hold a ceremony when a young student began reading the Haftiyak after memorizing a certain number of small surahs. Recently, instead of the Haftiyak, it has become customary to read and teach the complete Holy Quran directly.

"Haftiyak" is a book containing one-seventh of the Holy Quran and is one of the most important works in Islamic history. This work contains descriptions of portions of seven surahs from the Holy Quran.

The name "Haftiyak" comes from the words "haft" (seven) and "yak" (part), meaning "Haftiyak" is an important and integral book that constitutes one-seventh of the Holy Quran. This work is largely regarded as a text on the interpretation of religious writings.

The importance of the Haftiyak is manifested in the following:

1. Dividing the Holy Quran into parts: It supports scholarly and religious traditions in the process of studying and understanding the Quran.
2. The Science of Tafsir: This work has made a great contribution to the development of the science of tafsir, which helps to fully understand the meaning and content of the Holy Quran.
3. Its role in Islamic history: The Haftiyak was an important source for studying the Quran from a doctrinal perspective in early Islamic times.

The work contains some surahs from the Quran, each of which is enriched with deep tafsirs, commentaries, and explanations. This book is of great importance for Muslims not only for religious information but also from a scholarly perspective.

At the same time, the analysis of the Haftiyak is one of the necessary tools for a complete understanding of the Holy Quran and a comprehensive approach to its meaning and content. According to legends, "Kalila and Dimna" was actually written by Indian philosopher scholars in ancient times. It is based on Indian folklore and shares roots with "Panchatantra", "Hitopadesha", and other works.

The articles "Avesta" and "Haftiyak" play an important role in illuminating the earliest manifestations in the history of Uzbek children's reading. Through these articles, information is provided about the formation of children's literature of the ancient Uzbek people, its development process, and the specific aspects of children's culture. The Avesta is a sacred book of the Zoroastrian religion, containing a number of moral and spiritual ideas related to the upbringing of children. This book also contains thoughts aimed at teaching children moral values, truthfulness, and the right path.

"Haftiyak" is a poetic and artistic work written specifically for children, containing wise thoughts that promote spiritual, moral, aesthetic, and educational development in children. This work reveals the initial stages of children's literature, its significance, and goals.

In general, works such as "Avesta" and "Haftiyak" are of great importance in the formation of Uzbek children's reading, marking the starting point of moral, aesthetic, and educational ideas intended for children during this period.

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